

THE INNOVATIVE FIRM AS A SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEM

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the dynamics of organizational functioning from the perspective of open systems theory and behavioral sciences. It reveals the processes by which companies lose the ability to act effectively in a complex external environment and may eventually decline. The prerequisites for the accumulation of evolutionary changes and the implementation of a rapid radical transition through creative destruction to a new basic survival model are described. The importance of orienting activities toward innovative development within organizations of innovators and change leaders is emphasized. Recommendations are given for their training and retraining, as well as for changing the external institutional environment.

Introduction. The pace of socio-economic development of organizations, countries, and continents is accelerating. The duration of organizations' competitive activity is decreasing. Some successfully carry out timely modernization of their organizational model, often becoming essentially different entities. Others undergo complete destruction of hopelessly outdated models. Scientific justifications appear for economically irrational human behavior and for the role of leaders in modern innovative business. Research into the functioning of socio-economic systems is becoming deeper and more interdisciplinary. Increasing attention is paid to studying contemporary processes from the standpoint of general systems theory and the psychology of behavior of those who determine the future of organizations.

Review of scientific sources. The founder of general systems theory is considered to be the Austrian biologist Ludwig von Bertalanffy. He showed (1930) that any system exists thanks to its activity — interaction with the environment — exchange of energy, resources, etc. (Bertalanffy 1969) The system remains in a relatively balanced state only during its activity. Significant for systems theory is the work of Soviet scholar A.N. Malyuta “*Patterns of System Development*”, who introduced the concepts of equilibrium stable state — the stationary phase of system realization (second phase) — and dynamic states of change: the first (development and progress) and the third (decay and regression). He proposed the idea of a statistical state of the system as cyclical repetition of the same (running in circles). Dynamics, however, he interpreted as a spiral diverging in the first phase of system realization and converging in the third phase (Malyuta 1990). He substantiated this using mathematical apparatus and proposed graphical interpretation of these processes (Fig. 1).

Graves proposed a worldview system that makes holistic thinking and action possible. As he stated, “*an individual, a company, or society as a whole can respond positively only to those management principles, motivational appeals, educational methods, legal and ethical rules that are acceptable to the current level of human existence.*” Developing Graves' legacy, Don Beck

and Chris Cowan showed that “*the human spiral consists of intertwined chains of value systems, worldviews, and perspectives inherent to different eras and corresponding to different life conditions.*” However, in their works we observe only ascending spirals.

Figure 1. States of the system: left — dynamic development toward stable state (thickened ring); right — dynamic regression, contraction.

Psychologist Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, in *The Evolution of Personality*, described the processes of human behavioral formation by analogy with the formation of physical condition. He used the concept of the “meme,” introduced by Richard Dawkins in 1976 (*from Greek mimema — imitation of a thing*) (Dawkins 1989). Memes are considered cultural analogues of genes because they reproduce and mutate through natural selection (Wikipedia, Mem). “*Like genes, memes do not act alone but form mosaics, shaping a comprehensive view of human life and the surrounding world.*” (Beck & Cowan 2016: 131).

In *Spiral Dynamics*, Beck and Cowan, using an expanding spiral (Fig. 2), interpret the development of organizations in historical retrospect as the development of systems (Beck & Cowan 2016: 42-44). They show how the culture of society penetrates organizations together with employees, and how culture “exits” organizations into the external environment.

Compiled by the author based on materials by D. Beck, K. Cowan (Beck & Cowan 2016:68).

Figure 2. Graphical interpretation of organizational development in accordance with the culture of its main components.

Russian researcher V.M. Efimov clarifies: “*The choices individuals make today are embedded in the actions of yesterday’s volitional agents. At the same time... individuals, in addition to the rules imposed by ‘volitional agents,’ have their own informal rules and beliefs with deep historical roots. If these contradict the imposed rules, their implementation becomes*

doubtful.” (Efimov 2016: 49-64). He demonstrates the importance of timely legislative formalization of new behavior and of educational efforts by those interested in introducing these rules (Efimov 2016: 74-116). He shows that institutional change in modern society occurs step by step with each new law, rather than in leaps as we interpret revolutionary changes in socio-economic organizations. Graphically, this can be represented as movement along a triangle: from functioning to the emergence and testing of ideas by the advanced part of society; consolidation in the form of normative legal acts; habituation at a new level of behavior by other actors, and so on (Fig. 3).

Compiled by the author based on the idea of V.M. Efimov (Efimov 2016: 32).

Figure 3. Triangle of cycles of institutional change (the gray triangle reflects Russia’s prolonged “treading in the same institutional environment”).

Max Weber already drew attention to the need to develop rules of human behavior at the end of the 19th century, studying the processes of society’s transition from traditional to modern (Weber 1990). His research is known for examining the impact of cultural and religious factors on the formation of economic institutions and systems. He concluded that formalization of rules and procedures is significant in any social system. Applied to organizations, this means that every organization must have documents clearly regulating its functioning. It remains only to add the necessity of revising all these documents and other rules in accordance with changing strategies and culture.

Thus, by the beginning of the 21st century, a new socio-evolutionary theory had formed, called the theory of spiral dynamics.

Howard Bloom shows that the life process of organisms presupposes an inflow of matter from the environment, the type and volume of which are determined by the systemic characteristics of the organism. There is also an outflow of matter into the environment as a result of system functioning, which may be favorable or unfavorable for the external environment. Organisms secure additional energy that allows them to achieve negentropy and stability relative to the environment if they carry out activities acceptable to the external environment (Bloom 1995).

According to general systems theory, each component of a system must, on the one hand, each component of the system must subordinate its activity to the common interest, i.e., be guided by a common principle to ensure coordinated activity toward the unified goal of the system. This progressive systematization is characterized by the degree of connectedness of

elements. As a rule, such systematization is implemented through centralized management of organizational activity across the hierarchy, top-down. Accordingly, the leaders of this activity are considered **α -leaders**. However, at present there have appeared so-called *teal organizations* functioning without a middle layer of managers, which Frederic Laloux justified by the very high level of consciousness of their employees (Laloux 2016: 24-54).

On the other hand, most components of the system must retain their ability to respond to changing external conditions as necessary variety. Initially this was formulated by W. Ross Ashby for cybernetics: the variety of a complex system requires management that itself must possess the necessary variety (Ashby 1956). In general, this refers to the ability of system components to independently adapt to a changing external environment, and to adjust the entire system to new external conditions of activity. These are the regularities of changing internal connections to ensure progressive factorization (decentralization of decisions on overall system activity), which is characterized by the degree of independence of elements in implementing system-wide activity — **β** . Accordingly, leaders of such activity can be considered **β -leaders** (leaders of factorization) — innovators (Volkova & Denisov 2013), who, according to Everett Rogers, comprise about 2.5% of all participants. They are capable of going beyond existing knowledge and being the first to implement new behavior (Rogers 2003).

In Graves' spiral dynamics, abrupt changes in worldview and human behavior are interpreted as transitions in the virtual spiral from one side to the diametrically opposite side with increasing potential (see Fig. 2). A leap to a higher and broader turn of the virtual spiral arises from the accumulation of potential for change, the creation of conditions for these changes — the destruction of ties (relationships) hindering development, and the formation of ties of a new basis (*creative destruction*, according to Joseph Schumpeter) (Schumpeter 1995). This is a manifestation of Hegel's philosophical law — the transition of quantitative changes into a new quality. In human behavior, as shown, this does not occur instantaneously, but stepwise changes in the organizational model over a short period compared to many years of stable activity can quite reasonably be considered a revolutionary leap.

Methodology of research and result. The development of a socio-economic system in the external environment is proposed to be interpreted as virtual movement along spirally expanding rings (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Spiral dynamics of a socio-economic system in the external environment, subsystems within the system (each ring corresponds to a level of system development).

The fundamental results of such research were presented in the author's work "*Dynamics of Socio-Economic Systems*" (Kozlov 2018). Therefore, here we focus only on the conditions for transition to the next, qualitatively more significant stage of stable movement, or to the extinction of the system — the termination of activity as a whole.

It should be noted that the zone of relatively stable circular movement is very limited near $\alpha = \beta$ (highlighted in shading in Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Socio-economic system in the process of virtual movement with oscillations under alternating influence of progressive systematization (α , virtual force F_α) and progressive factorization (β , virtual force F_β), which in their alternating opposition ensure stable activity and adaptation to external environmental conditions.

Such constant opposition between systematization and factorization is vital for any dynamic system and corresponds to Hegel's philosophical law of the unity and struggle of opposites.

Circular movement remains relatively stable with some predominance of α over β if external resources are sufficient for survival within the existing organizational model and if the maximum possible share of system components is engaged in productive labor (see Fig. 5), with no more efficient competitors of comparable production volumes.

If the organizational model has exhausted its survival capacity but continues to strengthen systematization (centripetal forces F_α dominate, $\alpha > \beta$), this leads to accelerated movement along a tightening funnel-shaped spiral. The efficiency of resource transformation decreases, manifesting as non-competitiveness in the environment. Examples include firms such as Kodak and Xerox, which lost leading positions, retained only their brands, and shifted to insufficiently effective production and organizational technologies — not to mention companies that ceased to exist altogether.

Revealing the law of hierarchy, or hierarchical order, V.A. Engelhardt demonstrated with biological systems that a higher hierarchical level exerts guiding influence on the subordinate level. Subordinate members of the hierarchy acquire new properties, and as a result of these properties, a new "image of the whole" is formed (Engelhardt 1976). At the same time, as Arthur Koestler showed, every leader at each level, each node of the system, finds themselves in the situation of a "Janus-faced" role: the "face" directed toward the lower level has the character of an autonomous

whole (a system), subordinating those below and suppressing their independence; the “face” directed toward the node (apex) of the higher-level manifests properties of a dependent, adaptive part (Koestler 1969).

In a complex hierarchical system, as people adapt to these dual roles, their behavior is transformed. Centralization inevitably leads to increased subordination and suppression of independence of the components of the hierarchy. The volume of redundant information grows. The number of elements responsible for connections in the system, for information exchange rather than productive activity, multiplies (see Fig. 5, lower left). Overall, the efficiency of transforming resources from the environment for the benefit of the system decreases, especially when resources are stable or diminishing. For example, one can recall the changes experienced by the vertically over-organized Ford company with more than 110,000 employees in the 1970s, which lost competition to small Japanese assembly enterprises entering the U.S. market.

A different situation arises with timely engagement of the abilities of **β -leaders** (leaders of factorization), who identify and test innovations not only in production technologies but also in new behavior — organizational innovations. Rapid, though always stepwise, innovative change of the basis of the organizational model is ensured. This occurs, as Joseph Schumpeter noted, through creative destruction only of what prevents the implementation of new procedures of interaction in the organization (Schumpeter 1995). Human resources are primarily diverted to this, and the system as a whole cannot be maximally efficient (see Fig. 5, lower right, for graphical interpretation of role distribution among employees in this case). In place of destroyed connections, new ones are established, a new combination of all connections in the system is realized — a basic or improving organizational innovation.

Further, for the system to finally move to a higher level of stable activity (see Fig. 4), it is necessary for all employees to master new relationships and new procedures of interaction, with mandatory adjustment of internal documents and staff training. After this, relatively stable “circular movement” with slight predominance of α over β and maximum effect will again be carried out, until the next significant deviations from this state arise.

If the organization does not timely engage the abilities of β -leaders (who must still be found and assigned appropriate responsibilities), then, as Ichak Adizes notes, the organization will enter paralysis. In our interpretation, the organization will begin irreversibly and with acceleration to move toward extinction (Adizes 2014). In the interpretation suitable for this study, the life cycle of the organization, according to Adizes, looks as shown in Fig. 6.

The main point today is that the increasing pace of innovative development of business, industries, and the entire economy leads to a growing frequency of such innovative changes, while the duration of stable activity is decreasing.

Therefore, the presence of β -leaders in the management bodies of firms and other organizations becomes a necessary condition for survival in a rapidly changing external environment. Accordingly, organizations need not only design centers for product and process innovations. They need creative teams capable of tracking emerging deviations in the survival model and developing proactive proposals for adjusting the organizational model of the firm to changing external actors of the external environment, which at the moment of the “Moment

of Truth” (see Fig. 6), could ensure an innovative transition to a new organizational model. If a firm does not have sufficient resources to maintain enough factorization leaders, it must rely on the services of appropriate consultants on a permanent basis.

Figure 6. Life cycle of the organization and choice of further path of existence.

Consulting practice convincingly shows that proper optimization of management processes alone allows reduction of redundant elements of vertical organization and release of resources to support factorization leaders. Great opportunities open up for an organization when moving from the orange level to the green, and even greater ones when transitioning to a teal organization. At present, teal organizations are few worldwide. In Russia, only the Yekaterinburg consulting firm “Knopka” is known, where only one out of 4–5 employees hired through competitive selection remained working under conditions of highest responsibility and absence of middle management.

Conclusions. Every organization experiences periods of creation and establishment of activity, flourishing, and gradual decline of productive activity. The future of the system is revealed and shaped at the beginning of the decline stage. The struggle for self-preservation is usually associated with strengthening systematization, i.e., administration, and may be prolonged for a relatively long time. During this period, competitors may carry out necessary innovative reforms, and the changed external environment will leave no chance for the lagging organization to survive.

If timely reorientation of the organizational model’s activity occurs, with its active components shifting toward strengthening factorization through the activity of β -leaders, then a stepwise — evolutionary, yet rapid — transition to the next turn of development is carried out. In place of clearing — creative destruction of outdated organizational design, but not of the entire organizational model — a new one emerges. One system may be transformed into several more effective ones. This can be considered a revolutionary, radical change in the development of any organization, and even of communities or societies as a whole. Without such evolutionary accumulation of quantitative changes in the organizational model, both during rapid radical changes and afterwards, transition to a new quality is impossible.

The organizational model of any socio-economic system largely depends on the culture of the external environment, the entire state structure, since it is determined by the level of development of people's thinking. Individuals with a feudal paradigm of thinking position themselves as components of the state, entirely dependent on government authorities and employers. When they enter an organization, they are not inclined to take responsibility and are characterized by a certain deceitfulness in their behavior. Therefore, one cannot expect that many organizations will be able to find on the labor market the innovators and leaders of innovative development they need. Intensive training and retraining of personnel is necessary, including influencing the preparation of personnel in higher education.

It is necessary to influence the change of the external institutional environment in order to counteract the negative behavior of all citizens, and especially those who embody the apologists of this environment. It must be understood that without changing the external environment, we will not achieve the development of flexible, modern innovative green and teal organizations.

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